

MUCOCELE OF THE APPENDIX – A CASE REPORT**Dragos F. Voicu,***MD, PhD., Associated Profesor**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***Constantin Popazu,***MD, PhD.,**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***Alexandra Toma***MD, PhD.,**“Dunarea de Jos” University, Galati – Romania***Abstract**

Appendiceal mucocele is a rare but clinically significant condition characterized by abnormal accumulation of mucin within the lumen of the appendix. The entity ranges from benign retention cysts to malignant mucinous cystadenocarcinomas. We report a case of appendiceal mucocele diagnosed intraoperatively in a patient with non-specific abdominal pain.

Keywords: mucocele, appendectomy

Introduction

Research into the pathology of the cecal appendix, dominated by acute inflammation and its complications, has probably accumulated the most extensive world experience. The first successful appendectomy, known in history, was performed in 1735, by the english surgeon Claude Amyand, in an 11-year-old patient with a strangulated inguinal hernia, which led to the discovery and removal of the acutely inflamed appendix, located in the hernial sac.

Appendiceal mucocele is an uncommon pathology, reported in approximately 0.2–0.7% of appendectomy specimens. The condition is often discovered incidentally during surgery or imaging performed for unrelated indications. While some mucocèles are benign, others may harbor neoplastic changes, and rupture can lead to pseudomyxoma peritonei, a serious complication. Awareness and recognition are essential for appropriate surgical management.

Case report

A 45-year-old female presented with intermittent right lower quadrant abdominal pain for three months, associated with occasional nausea. There was no history of fever, weight loss, or altered bowel habits.

Clinical examination revealed mild tenderness in the right iliac fossa, without rebound or palpable mass.

Laboratory investigations were within normal limits.

Imaging:

-ultrasound of the abdomen demonstrated a cystic, tubular structure in the right iliac fossa.

-CT scan revealed a well-encapsulated, low-attenuation lesion measuring 6/ 3 cm, contiguous with the cecum, suggestive of appendiceal mucocele (fig.1)

Fig.1

Surgery:

The patient underwent a laparoscopic appendectomy. Intraoperatively, the appendix was found to be dilated and cystic, measuring 6 cm in length. There was no evidence of rupture, peritoneal spread, or lymphadenopathy. Appendectomy was performed. There were no postoperative complications, and follow-up imaging at 6 months showed no recurrence.

Histopathology:

Microscopic examination showed a mucin-filled dilated appendix with flattened epithelium, consistent with simple appendiceal mucocele - retention cyst (fig.2). No evidence of dysplasia or malignancy was observed.

Fig. 2

Discussion

Appendiceal mucocele represents a spectrum of diseases, ranging from non-neoplastic retention cysts to mucinous cystadenoma and cystadenocarcinoma. The clinical presentation is often nonspecific, and many cases are incidentally diagnosed. Radiologic evaluation is valuable in preoperative detection, though definitive diagnosis relies on histopathology.

Appendectomy is adequate for benign mucoceles without evidence of malignancy.

Right hemicolectomy may be indicated in cases with confirmed malignant transformation, involvement of the cecal wall, or positive lymph nodes. Avoiding rupture during surgery is crucial to prevent pseudomyxoma peritonei.

Conclusion

Appendiceal mucocele, though rare, should be considered in the differential diagnosis of cystic right iliac fossa lesions. Preoperative suspicion, careful surgical technique, and histopathological evaluation are essential to guide management and prevent complications.

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